

Advancing justicidin B delivery by cinnamyl-functionalized polymeric micelles

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Abstract

Justicidin B (JB) is a biologically active aryl-naphthalene lignan with significant therapeutic potential. However, its clinical application is limited by poor solubility and stability. In this study, cinnamyl-functionalized polyglycidol-poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PG-PCL) polymeric micelles are developed and evaluated as nanocarriers for JB delivery. Both modified and non-modified micelles formed stable nanosystems (<150 nm, low polydispersity), suitable for systemic administration. Notably, cinnamyl-functionalized micelles demonstrated superior encapsulation efficiency compared to non-modified systems, along with enhanced stability over 2 months. Drug release studies revealed a reduced burst effect and a more controlled, sustained release profile for cinnamyl-modified micelles. *In vitro* cytotoxicity assays showed significantly improved antiproliferative activity against HL-60 leukemia cells ($IC_{50} = 3.65 \mu\text{g/mL}$) compared to free JB ($IC_{50} = 6.65 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and non-modified micelles ($IC_{50} = 9.14 \mu\text{g/mL}$), while maintaining low toxicity toward normal cells. These findings highlight cinnamyl-functionalized micelles as a promising platform for enhancing the therapeutic performance of hydrophobic anticancer agents.

Keywords

Cinnamyl-modified copolymers, cytotoxicity, enhanced encapsulation, justicidin B, polymeric micelles, targeted delivery

Introduction

The development of efficient therapeutic strategies still poses a serious challenge in modern medicine, especially in the fields of cancer and infectious disease therapy. Although numerous pharmacological advancements have been made during the past decades, many drugs are still subject to certain limitations, including poor selectivity, systemic toxicity, and the development of drug resistance

(Sell et al. 2023). All these factors emphasize the necessity to explore novel therapeutic approaches and new drug delivery systems to enhance the pharmacological activity and safety of drugs (Jain et al. 2024; Varghese et al. 2026).

Plants are currently considered one of the most promising sources of bioactive compounds, being rich in diverse classes of potent biomolecules with significant potential as drug candidates (Burgberger et al. 2025). Among these, lignans represent an important group of secondary

metabolites characterized by structural diversity and a broad spectrum of biological effects. Justicidin B (JB) is a member of the arylnaphthalene lignan group of natural products found in many plants. As a result of extensive studies, JB has been proven to possess a wide variety of pharmacological properties, including anticancer, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory effects. It should be noted that its mechanism of action is based on apoptosis induction, cell proliferation inhibition, and regulation of signaling pathways (Hemmati and Seradj 2016). At the same time, the clinical use of JB is limited by several intrinsic characteristics of this compound, including pronounced hydrophobicity, which negatively affects its solubility and, as a result, makes it difficult to deliver the drug into the body and transport it to the target area (Gertsch et al. 2003). The presence of additional problems, such as its rapid metabolism and instability under physiological conditions, adds to the difficulties in drug delivery. For this reason, the creation of an effective delivery system is necessary to increase drug solubility, protect it from degradation, and achieve controlled release.

One of the most promising strategies for overcoming drug delivery problems is to develop nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems (Xu et al. 2023). Polymeric micelles are examples of such a class of delivery systems, which are nanoparticles with a core-shell architecture created from amphiphilic biodegradable block copolymers in an aqueous environment. Polymeric micelles are characterized by a hydrophobic core and hydrophilic shell, where the hydrophobic core acts as a reservoir for poorly soluble drugs, while the hydrophilic corona provides steric stabilization, improves colloidal stability, and prolongs systemic circulation (Figueiras et al. 2022). As a result, polymeric micelles can significantly enhance drug solubilization, protect labile molecules from degradation, and improve pharmacokinetic and biodistribution profiles, ultimately increasing therapeutic efficacy. In addition, based on their specific physicochemical properties and nanoscale dimensions, polymeric micelles demonstrate improved pharmacokinetics and passive targeting via the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, which leads to better drug distribution in pathological sites (Rajabi and Feyzbakhsh 2025). Typically, the hydrophobic core is formed by aliphatic polyesters, such as poly(lactide-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA); however, their hydrolytic degradation generates acidic by-products that may locally decrease pH and may induce inflammatory responses in surrounding tissues. In this context, researchers have focused on developing alternative hydrophobic segments that exhibit more neutral degradation profiles while maintaining biocompatibility and structural integrity (Turnovská and Etrych 2025). Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL)-based copolymers exemplify an attractive alternative to PLGA due to their slower degradation and reduced tendency to produce acidic degradation products. PCL-containing micellar cores can provide a more stable and physiologically compatible microenvironment for drug delivery. Furthermore, PCL-based amphiphilic

diblock and triblock systems have demonstrated excellent self-assembly abilities, high drug-loading capacity, and sustained release profiles, making them high-potential candidates for long-circulating nanocarriers in biomedical applications (Bhadran et al. 2023). While the selection of biocompatible, non-acidifying core-forming polymers such as PCL is crucial, further improvements in micellar performance can be achieved through rational chemical modification of the polymer backbone. Consequently, cinnamyl-modified polymers have emerged as a particularly promising class of materials. The incorporation of cinnamyl moieties introduces aromatic and hydrophobic domains capable of promoting π - π stacking and hydrophobic interactions with drug molecules (Kalinova et al. 2020). These interactions enhance drug-polymer affinity, leading to improved encapsulation efficiency, increased micellar stability, and better controlled release behavior. In addition, cinnamyl functionalization can strengthen the integrity of the micellar core, thereby reducing premature drug leakage under physiological conditions. Cinnamyl-modified polymeric micelles have demonstrated strong potential as delivery systems for hydrophobic compounds. In a previous study, the successful development of cinnamyl-functionalized micelles for the delivery of cannabidiol (CBD) was reported, which resulted in improved solubility, enhanced encapsulation efficiency, and beneficial physicochemical characteristics. These findings confirm the effectiveness of cinnamyl modification in improving micellar drug delivery performance and support its applicability to other hydrophobic bioactive molecules such as JB (Toncheva-Moncheva et al. 2023).

The present study employs cinnamyl-modified polymeric micelles for the encapsulation and delivery of JB, aiming to enhance its solubility, stability, and therapeutic potential. To the best of current knowledge, this is the first study describing the preparation, physicochemical characterization, and drug-loading performance of cinnamyl-modified micelles as a delivery platform for JB.

Materials and methods

General experimental procedures

JB previously isolated from *in vitro* hairy root cultures of *L. leonii* was quantified by LC-HRESI-MS using an external standard method with a purified reference compound (Nedelcheva et al. 2024). Linear amphiphilic copolymers based on poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) and polyglycidol (PG), including both non-modified and cinnamyl-modified systems, were synthesized and characterized as described elsewhere (Toncheva-Moncheva et al. 2019, 2023). Deionized water was obtained using a Millipore MilliQ system (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and additionally filtered through a 220 nm PTFE filter and a 20 nm cellulose filter. Absolute ethanol, chloroform, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, Spectra/Por® dialysis membrane (molecular weight cutoff (MWCO) 12,000–14,000 Da), RPMI

culture medium, trypsin, and fetal calf serum were purchased from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). The chemicals, reagents, and culture media used were of analytical grade or suitable for cell culture.

Cell lines and culture conditions

The antiproliferative activity of JB and its micellar formulations was studied *in vitro* on the human tumor cell line HL-60 (acute myeloid leukemia), purchased from the German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (DSMZ GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany). In parallel, the cytotoxic potential of the newly synthesized copolymers was also evaluated on normal mouse fibroblasts CCL-1 (NCTC 929, American Type Culture Collection—ATCC, USA). HL-60 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 5% L-glutamine. The culture was performed under standard conditions—temperature 37 °C and an atmosphere containing 5% humidified CO₂. CCL-1 cells were cultured in accordance with the requirements of ISO 10993-5, Annex C (ISO 10993-5:2009/2017). They were grown in Eagle's Minimum Essential Medium (MEM-A, Capricorn®, Germany) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated horse serum and 2 mM L-glutamine (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), under culture conditions identical to those for HL-60 cells.

Synthesis of copolymers

The copolymers were obtained via a click-chemistry approach based on azide–alkyne coupling between monoalkyne-functionalized poly(ethoxyethyl glycidyl ether) (PEEGE, Mn ≈ 6300 g·mol⁻¹, Đ ≈ 1.2 for the non-modified copolymer, and Mn ≈ 6700 g·mol⁻¹, Đ ≈ 1.1 for the cinnamyl-modified copolymer) and bifunctional azide-terminated poly(ε-caprolactone) (PCL) derivatives. The cinnamyl-modified PCL precursor exhibited Mn ≈ 4800 g·mol⁻¹ (Đ ≈ 1.35), while the non-modified PCL₃₅ analogue possessed comparable molar mass characteristics (Mn 4300 g·mol⁻¹, Đ ≈ 1.3). Subsequent hydrolysis of the protective ethoxyethyl groups yielded PG-based block copolymers. This synthetic strategy enables precise control over composition and macromolecular architecture.

The non-modified copolymer PG₄₅-block-PCL₃₅-block-PG₄₅ exhibited a number-average molar mass Mn ≈ 11,000 g·mol⁻¹ (Đ ≈ 1.8), while the cinnamyl-modified copolymer PG₅₀-block-PPO₄-block-[P(CyCL)₄-co-(CL)₄₀]-block-PPO₄-block-PG₅₀ showed Mn ≈ 13,200 g·mol⁻¹ (Đ ≈ 1.3). The resulting amphiphilic structures are capable of self-assembly into micellar systems suitable for drug encapsulation and controlled release applications (Moncheva-Toncheva et al. 2019, 2023).

Preparation of empty and JB-loaded polymer micelles

The nanoprecipitation method was employed as the main approach for the preparation of both blank and JB-load-

ed micelles. A blank copolymer solution (6 mg of copolymer dissolved in 3 mL methanol) was added dropwise to ultrapure water (Milli-Q system, Type I) (3 mL) at room temperature. After 30 min, the organic solvent was removed by evaporation under reduced pressure at 37 °C to obtain a slightly opalescent micellar dispersion with a final concentration of 2 mg/mL. Drug-loaded micelles were prepared following the same procedure as for the blank micelles. The copolymer (6 mg) was dissolved in 3 mL of methanol, and a solution of JB (0.6 mg in 110 μL of chloroform) was added. The resulting mixture was added dropwise to 3 mL of ultrapure water (Milli-Q system, Type I) at room temperature under vigorous stirring (1000 rpm) for 30 min. The organic solvents were removed by evaporation under reduced pressure at 37 °C, yielding a slightly opalescent aqueous micellar dispersion with final concentrations of 2 mg/mL polymer and 0.2 mg/mL drug (JB:copolymer = 1:10).

Characterization of empty and JB-loaded micelles

Dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering (DLS and ELS)

The size, size distribution patterns, and ζ-potential of the prepared micellar formulations were determined by DLS and ELS measurements on a NanoBrook 90Plus PALS instrument (Brookhaven Instruments Corporation, Nashua, NH, USA) equipped with a 35 mW red diode laser (λ = 640 nm). DLS measurements were carried out at a scattering angle (θ) of 90°, while the ζ-potential measurements were carried out at a scattering angle (θ) of 15°. All measurements were performed at a temperature of 25 °C. The hydrodynamic diameter, Dh, was calculated using the Stokes–Einstein equation. The ζ-potentials were calculated from the obtained electrophoretic mobility by the Smoluchowski equation using the PALS method.

Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA)

NTA measurements were performed on a NanoSight Pro analyzer (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, United Kingdom) equipped with a high-sensitivity sCMOS camera. A 55 mW blue diode laser operated at 488 nm was used. The micellar dispersions were analyzed directly without prior dilution. The samples were injected with sterile syringes through a NanoSight syringe pump (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, UK), providing a continuous flow of particles (flow rate: 3 μL·min⁻¹) into the sample chamber. Measurements were performed at room temperature. The NanoSight Pro v1.0 software (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, UK) was used for data analysis.

Quantification of JB

For the quantitative determination of JB, an LC-HRESI-MS method was developed and validated. In the LC-HRESI-MS analysis, JB was detected as a protonated molecular

Figure 1. Calibration curve of JB.

ion at m/z 365.1014 $[M+H]^+$, consistent with the molecular formula $C_{21}H_{17}O_6^+$ (calcd. for m/z 365.1020). Quantification was performed using an external calibration curve constructed from a purified JB standard. The method demonstrated satisfactory linearity over the investigated concentration range (Fig. 1), with a correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.9999. Regression analysis was subsequently applied, and the corresponding calibration equation and coefficient of determination are presented in Table 1. The amount of JB was calculated using the calibration equation $y = 498940x - 850372$.

Determination of JB encapsulation efficacy (EE %)

JB encapsulation efficiency was quantified by ultracentrifugation of aliquots of micellar nanosuspensions at $100,000 \times g$ for 5 min to separate the non-entrapped drug. The supernatant containing free non-encapsulated JB was collected and subjected to quantitative analysis by LC-HRESI-MS using a pre-built calibration curve. The loading efficiency (EE%) was calculated using the formula:

$$EE\% = \frac{Mt - Mf}{Mt} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where Mt is the total amount of JB used in the preparation of micelles and Mf is the free drug.

In vitro JB release

The release profiles of JB were evaluated using the dialysis bag diffusion method. Briefly, 1 mL aliquots of micellar nanosuspensions loaded with JB (equivalent to 200 μg of JB) were transferred into dialysis bags (MWCO 12,000–14,000 Da; Spectra/Por®). The dialysis bags were then immersed in 50 mL of release medium consisting of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) supplemented with 5% ethanol to maintain sink conditions. The system was maintained under continuous stirring at 100 rpm and a controlled temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C. At predetermined time intervals, 1 mL samples were withdrawn from the release medi-

Table 1. Determination coefficient and regression equations of JB.

Parameters	Justicidin B
Determination coefficient	$r^2 = 0.9999$
Linear range (ng/mL)	3.94–98.50
Regression equations	$y = 498940x - 850372$
Number of standards	5

um and analyzed for JB content using LC-HRESI-MS. The concentration of JB was determined based on a previously established calibration curve, which exhibited linearity over the range of 3–100 ng/mL ($R^2 = 0.9999$).

Stability evaluation

The physical stability of the prepared JB-loaded micellar formulations was assessed by monitoring changes in key physicochemical parameters, including particle size (D_h), polydispersity index (PDI), zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency (EE%), following storage under refrigerated conditions (4 ± 2 °C) for 1 month. In addition, the formulations were visually inspected to detect any alterations in their macroscopic appearance.

MTT colorimetric assay

The *in vitro* antiproliferative activity of JB loaded into PG-PCL-PG or cinnamyl-modified PG-PCL-cy-PG micelles, or its free drug form in ethanol solution, was evaluated using a validated cell viability assay, namely the MTT test—with minor modifications (Konstantinov et al. 1999). In this assay, the yellow tetrazolium salt MTT is converted into a violet formazan product, insoluble crystals, by the mitochondrial enzyme succinate dehydrogenase of viable cells.

HL-60 or CCL-1 cells in the exponential phase of growth were seeded in 96-well plates (100 μL per well) at a density of 10^5 cells and incubated for 24 h under standard conditions. Thereafter, they were treated with increasing concentrations of micellar or free JB (6.25, 12.5, 20, 54.2, and 100 μM). Following 72 h of treatment, a sterile MTT substrate solution (10 μL per well, 10 mg/mL in PBS) was

Table 2. Composition and molar mass characteristics of the used block copolymers.

Copolymer	Abbreviation	M_n^a (g.mol ⁻¹)	M_w/M_n^b	CMC (mg/mL)
PG ₄₅ - <i>b</i> -PCL ₃₅ - <i>b</i> -PG ₄₅	PG-PCL-PG	11,000	1.8	0.10
PG ₅₀ - <i>b</i> -PPO ₄ - <i>b</i> -[P(CyCL) ₄ - <i>co</i> -(CL) ₄₀]- <i>b</i> -PPO ₄ - <i>b</i> -PG ₅₀	PG-PCL _{cy} -PG	13,200	1.3	0.12

^anumber-averaged molar mass from ¹H NMR. ^b M_w/M_n —molar mass distribution from SEC.

Table 3. Physicochemical characteristics determined by dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering (DLS and ELS) and encapsulation efficiency (EE%) of JB-loaded polymeric micelles at preparation and after 2 months of storage at 4 °C.

Sample	At initial preparation			
	Size (nm)	PDI	ζ-potential (mV)	EE (%)
PG-PCL-PG empty	104 ± 1.7	0.12 ± 0.01	-	-
PG-PCL-PG:JustB	108 ± 3.5	0.116 ± 0.03	-3.92 ± 0.95	97.5
PG-PCLcy-PG empty	120 ± 2	0.096 ± 0.02	-5.90 ± 1.23	-
PG-PCLcy-PG:JustB	141 ± 3.5	0.124 ± 0.05	-6.18 ± 0.81	99.5 ± 1.81
After 2 months of storage				
PG-PCL-PG:JustB loaded	108 ± 2.5	0.125 ± 0.02	-4.12 ± 0.95	87.8 ± 1.95
PG-PCLcy-PG:JustB loaded	140 ± 3.5	0.141 ± 0.01	-6.48 ± 0.81	98.5 ± 2.3

added to each well. The cells were further incubated for 4 h, after which 100 μL of isopropyl alcohol containing 5% formic acid was added to each well to dissolve the formed formazan crystals. The absorbance of the resulting solutions was measured at 580 nm. Cell viability was calculated as a percentage relative to the untreated control group, defined as 100% viability, and presented as concentration-effect curves, from which the half-maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) were determined.

Results and discussion

In this study, two linear amphiphilic copolymers based on poly(ε-caprolactone) (PCL) and polyglycidol (PG), namely non-modified and cinnamyl-modified PCL/PG systems, were synthesized and applied for the preparation of drug delivery nanocarriers, with emphasis on the effect of cinnamyl functionalization on their self-assembly and release behavior. The copolymers possess comparable molar masses and critical micelle concentrations (CMCs) (Table 2).

The reference nonmodified and cinnamyl-modified copolymers self-assembled into well-defined micellar nanostructures in aqueous solution (Moncheva-Toncheva et al. 2019). The rationale for employing these specific copolymers lies in the ability of the hydrophobic PCL block to undergo crystallization, leading to the formation of so-called kinetically “frozen” micelles. In such systems, the exchange of polymer chains between individual micelles is significantly restricted. It has been demonstrated that these micelles retain their structural integrity even upon dilution below the CMC, thereby ensuring remarkable stability in highly diluted environments—an important prerequisite for enhanced intracellular uptake in tumor cells (Yu et al. 2010). Furthermore, the presence of cinnamyl pendant moieties in the modified copolymer is a prerequisite for additional compaction and stabilization of the micelle core while achieving higher encapsulation of hydrophobic drugs and controlled release, respectively, without loss of colloidal stability.

It was hypothesized that the combination of a crystallizable PCL segment and aromatic cinnamyl fragments likely leads to a synergistic effect, facilitating the formation of thermodynamically stable micellar nanostructures with enhanced loading capacity for the hydrophobic compound JB. The topology of the copolymers used is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the architecture of cinnamyl-modified block copolymer.

Characterization of empty and JB-loaded micelles

All polymeric micelles were obtained by nanoprecipitation at polymer concentrations approximately one order of magnitude above the CMC, as described in the preparation section. The micellar size and PDI were determined by DLS, and the ζ-potential by ELS. The results obtained are presented in Table 3 and Fig. 3.

The physicochemical characterization of the prepared micelles showed that both copolymers form monomodal micellar dispersions with a low PDI (PDI < 0.15) and a hydrodynamic diameter below 150 nm, consistent with nanoparticles suitable for systemic application.

A slight increase in size was observed for cinnamyl-modified micelles compared to their non-modified counterparts. This can be attributed to the increased hydrophobicity and steric bulk introduced by the cinnamyl groups, which may reduce the packing efficiency within the hydrophobic core, resulting in an expanded micellar structure.

JB encapsulation into micelles is associated with a further increase in micellar size, more pronounced for

Figure 3. Hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) distributions of blank and JB-loaded micellar nanoparticles, determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS, intensity) and nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA, number-weighted size distribution and particle concentration) of PG-PCLcy-PG-based micellar systems.

cinnamyl-modified micelles, likely due to their increased hydrophobicity and lower intrinsic packing efficiency, which facilitate higher drug incorporation and additional core expansion (Table 3). Notably, despite these increases, the micelle size remained below 150 nm in all cases.

For a more detailed physicochemical characterization, the resulting loaded micelles were also investigated by NTA. The data for average hydrodynamic size (D_{mean} calculated from particle number) and particle concentration determined by NTA are shown in Fig. 3 and confirm the results obtained by DLS. The D_{mean} indicator, reflecting the average particle size, shows good comparability with the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) determined by DLS (Fig. 3). For JB-loaded cinnamyl-modified micelles, a D_{mean} value of approximately 170 nm with a small standard deviation (≈ 8 nm) was observed, confirming the homogeneity of the system.

Encapsulation efficacy

JB-loaded micelles were prepared by the nanoprecipitation method at a copolymer-to-drug mass ratio of 10:1. Both micellar formulations are characterized by high drug

encapsulation above 90% (Table 3), which confirms the strong hydrophobic interactions between JB molecules and the PCL core. The hydrophobic aromatic nature of JB facilitates its incorporation into the PCL core. Notably, the incorporation of cinnamyl moieties into the copolymer further enhanced encapsulation efficiency, reaching up to 99.5%. This improvement can be attributed not only to increased hydrophobicity but also to specific π - π stacking interactions between the aromatic cinnamyl groups and the fused aromatic system of JB. These interactions promote tighter molecular packing within the micellar core and reduce drug expulsion during nanoprecipitation. Thus, a synergistic effect between hydrophobic interactions and directional π - π stacking contributes to the superior loading capacity of the modified system (Shi et al. 2013).

Stability evaluation

An integral part of the characterization of nanoscale drug delivery systems is the assessment of their storage stability. For this purpose, the prepared JB-loaded micelles were stored at 4 °C for 2 months, and their key parameters—size, size distribution, polydispersity index, and encapsu-

lation efficiency—were monitored and recorded. After the storage period ended, these parameters were compared to their initial values measured immediately after preparation of the micelles. The results are shown in Table 3.

As evident from the presented results, after 2 months of storage at 4 °C, no statistically significant changes in the size of the micelles were observed; the size increase was not higher than 5% compared to the initial values, which confirms high colloidal stability and lack of aggregation. The polydispersity indices (PDI = 0.12–0.15) remained low and close to the initial values, demonstrating that the size distribution remained monomodal and the systems maintained their uniformity over time. These results provide evidence that the combination of a hydrophobic crystallizing PCL core and a hydrophilic polyglycidol crown provides structurally stable micelles in which fusion or Ostwald ripening processes practically do not occur at low temperatures (Owen et al. 2012). Regarding encapsulation efficiency, there is clear evidence that cinnamyl-modified micelles maintained their high loading efficiency for JB. The improved retention of JB in cinnamyl-modified micelles can be attributed to the combined effect of hydrophobic interactions and π – π stacking, which reduce drug mobility within the core and limit its diffusion into the aqueous phase during storage.

In vitro release profiles of JB

The release profiles of JB were evaluated by the dialysis method against 50 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as the acceptor phase at 37 ± 0.5 °C. The obtained profiles are shown in Fig. 4.

As evident from the presented results, the release of JB exhibits distinct differences between cinnamyl-modified and non-modified micelles, both in terms of the total amount released and the shape of the release profiles. The release from the non-modified micelles is characterized by an initial burst effect of approximately 31% of the encapsulated JB released within the first hour. In contrast,

Figure 4. Release profiles of JB from non-modified and cinnamyl-modified micelles at 37 °C.

the cinnamyl-functionalized counterparts display a more gradual and near-linear release profile. These differences can be attributed to variations in the internal structure and packing density of the micellar core. The presence of cinnamyl groups introduces specific π – π stacking interactions with the aromatic structure of JB, leading to stronger and more directional drug–polymer association. These interactions increase the energetic barrier for drug diffusion and promote a more compact and ordered core structure.

Additionally, the increased hydrophobic character of the modified core further reduces water penetration, limiting core swelling and slowing drug diffusion. As a result, the release profile shifts from burst-dominated to more controlled, near-linear behavior. At the same time, this does not appear to enforce a harsh diffusional barrier, as the linear architecture of the copolymer allows a certain degree of chain mobility and partial relaxation of the core structure. Altogether, a more controlled and sustained release profile is achieved, which is beneficial for maintaining therapeutic drug concentrations over a prolonged period.

Cytotoxicity evaluation

In the next stage of the study, the antiproliferative activity and cytotoxic potential of the elaborated JB-loaded micelles were evaluated in comparison with the free agent.

JB is a natural derivative with proven antitumor activity (Momekov et al. 2011), but its limited aqueous solubility and instability in biological media hinder its clinical translation potential. Consequently, loading it into polymeric micelles can improve its pharmaceutical availability, prolong its circulation time, and limit nonspecific toxicity to healthy cells. Accordingly, the cytotoxic potential of formulated versus free JB was evaluated in two cell lines: HL-60, a human acute leukemia cell line, and CCL-1, a non-tumorigenic mouse fibroblast cell line. These cell models were selected to compare the activity of the investigated micellar nanosuspensions in malignant cells with their effects on non-malignant cells, providing an initial indication of tumor selectivity and general cytocompatibility. Although this simplified *in vitro* setup does not fully reflect the complexity of systemic exposure *in vivo*, it offers useful preliminary insight into the safety and selectivity profile of the developed micellar formulations.

The cytotoxic potential was analyzed using a standard MTT test for assessing cell viability. The resulting concentration-effect curves are shown in Fig. 5, and the calculated corresponding equieffective concentrations are presented in Table 4.

The results clearly show that both JB-loaded micellar formulations exhibit dose-dependent cytotoxicity against the studied cell lines HL-60 and CCL-1 (Fig. 5). This demonstrates the preserved antiproliferative activity of JB upon encapsulation. The calculated IC_{50} values unambiguously indicate that cinnamyl functionalization of the copolymer has a significant impact on the cytotoxic effect of micelle-encapsulated JB (Table 4).

Figure 5. Concentration–response curves after 72 h exposure of HL-60 and CCL-1 cells to varying concentrations of empty micelles (upper panel) or JB-loaded micelles (lower panel). Data are presented as means \pm SEM from three independent experiments.

Table 4. Equieffective concentrations calculated after nonlinear regression of concentration–effect curves (IC_{50}).

Cell line	IC_{50} (mg/mL)				
	Justicidin B	PG-PCLcy-PG:JustB	PG-PCL-PG:JustB	PG-PCLcy-PG empty	PG-PCL-PG empty
CCL-1	18.85 \pm 1.5	19.45 \pm 2.7	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
HL-60	6.65 \pm 1.1	3.65 \pm 1.05	9.14 \pm 2.7	N.D.	N.D.

The highest antiproliferative activity was observed in PG-PCLcy-PG micelles (IC_{50} = 3.65 μ g/mL), which is superior compared to both free JB (IC_{50} = 6.65 μ g/mL) and drug encapsulated in non-modified micelles (IC_{50} = 9.14 μ g/mL). This finding could be explained by stronger interaction of the linear, cinnamyl-modified copolymer with the cell membrane and consequent release of the active substance near the cell surface. In addition, the aromatic cinnamyl groups could enhance the hydrophobic interactions with the lipid bilayer, promoting intracellular entry and a more pronounced inhibitory effect of JB. Comparative analysis of cytotoxicity against normal fibroblasts (CCL-1) and tumor HL-60 cells revealed a clear trend toward selectivity of the developed formulations. Both loaded systems exhibited significantly higher toxicity against the tumor cell line, while the effect on normal cells was limited, with IC_{50} values remaining consistently higher or even not reaching 50% destruction of the cell populations. This indicates that loading JB in PG-PCL-PG micelles may reduce its nonspecific cytotoxicity while maintaining or

even enhancing its effect on tumor cells. Such a selective effect can be explained by the differences in membrane permeability and metabolic activity between tumor and normal cells, as well as the increased endocytic activity of tumor cells, which favors the intracellular accumulation of micelles (Kwon and Kataoka 2012).

An interesting finding from the performed cytotoxic assay is that empty PG-PCLcy-PG and PG-PCL-PG micelles show only marginal cytotoxicity, inhibiting cell viability by less than 20%. This demonstrates the high biocompatibility of the developed carriers and the lack of inherent cytotoxic potential of the copolymers, which is a key prerequisite for their potential application as drug carriers.

Conclusion

In this study, non-modified and cinnamyl-functionalized polyglycidol–poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PG–PCL) block copolymer micelles were successfully developed as nanocarriers

for JB delivery. The obtained micelles demonstrated excellent physicochemical characteristics and high drug encapsulation efficiency, which was further enhanced in the cinnamyl-modified formulation. In addition, the elaborated micelles exhibited prolonged JB release. Cytotoxicity evaluation confirmed that both micellar formulations preserved the intrinsic antiproliferative activity of JB and exhibited dose-dependent cytotoxicity against malignant HL-60 cells, with cinnamyl-functionalized micelles outperforming both free JB and non-modified micellar formulations. Therefore, it can be concluded that cinnamyl-functionalized PG–PCL micelles represent a promising drug delivery platform for hydrophobic bioactive compounds such as JB, providing improved loading efficiency, controlled release, and enhanced antiproliferative activity.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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- The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.
- The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.
- The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.
- The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI. No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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